

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D9.3

Report on Training Events Y1

WP9 – T9.4

Technical reference

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

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Document history

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Version 0.5	05.04.2023	Carla Trindade Costa, INSA João Paulo Teixeira, INSA	First draft
Version 1	05.05.2023	Task 9.4 partners (indicated in contributors' section)	Finalized draft version
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Version 3	11.10.2023	European Commission	Alteration in data presentation format; minor alterations to text

Abstract

Task 9.4 “Training” aims to develop individual and institutional capacities and training programs of partners and stakeholders on PARC scientific topics. In Y1, task 9.4 efforts were dedicated to the identification of training needs using an online survey; a description of topics identified, alongside their importance, target audience, and difficulty level is now presented in this report. The most frequently indicated topics were: (1) Risk assessment – fundamentals and approaches; (2) Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data; (3) Databases (concepts, structure, construction, hosting, etc.); (4) New approach methodologies (NAMs); (5) Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs); and (6) Statistical analysis (biostatistics for epidemiology and ecotoxicology). The information collected will be crucial for Task 9.4 forthcoming activities that include mapping of existing training and the definition of a training plan for Y2 and Y3. Information on training courses carried out within each PARC WP in Y1 is also listed here.

Keywords

Capacity-building; training needs; training plan; courses; online resources; online survey

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Abbreviation list

AOP: Adverse Outcome Pathway

BKMR: Bayesian Multiple Index Models

FAIR: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

GFF: GO FAIR Foundation

HBM: Human Biomonitoring

MCRA: Monte Carlo Risk Assessment toolbox

NAMs: New Approach Methodologies

NGRA: Next-Generation Risk Assessment

PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic

RPF: Relative Potency Factor

SQL: Structured Query Language

WP: Work Package

1. Task 9.4 Training – overview of aims and activities

In alignment with PARC's objectives, Task 9.4 "Training" of WP9 - *Building infrastructural and human capacities* will support the development of capacities and training programs in PARC scientific-related topics.

Task 9.4 aims to provide PARC partners and stakeholders the opportunity to obtain and/or increase the skills needed for the implementation of the activities prioritized in PARC, and thereby contribute to interdisciplinary capacity-building. It is also expected to build and strengthen research capacity of stakeholders and partners by promoting knowledge exchange and by contributing to their skills' development; their ability to undertake high-quality research; their capacities to apply new tools and methodologies developed in PARC; to increase their understanding of the latest developments on PARC topics; and their preparedness to address current and new challenges in the field of chemical risk assessment and thereby support decision-making.

In the first year of PARC, training needs were identified *via* a dedicated online survey distributed to institutions through National Hub Contact Points (NHCP), and results are now presented in this deliverable.

In the coming months (May-October 2023), building on data obtained in this training needs assessment survey, partners will work to systematize the identified gaps in trainings by 1) mapping available training (outside PARC) and resources on the topics identified; and 2) prioritizing and setting the training courses and online learning resources to be held/developed within PARC in Y2 and Y3. In parallel, supporting materials will be produced and provided to local training organizers (see "[Materials' development to support future training](#)" for further information).

Considering the duration of PARC, there will be two additional assessments of training needs (M40 and M64) that will result in two renewed training plans (by M42 and M66). With this strategy, we expect to have a more flexible, evolving, and dynamic training plan, adjusted to PARC progress and findings.

2. Training needs identification

2.1 Survey description

A PARC "Training Needs" online Survey was initially drafted by INSA (task leader), and then discussed and refined with all partners involved in the survey development activity (ANSES, FR; INRAE, FR; ONIRIS, FR; BRGM, FR; LNE, FR; UMIT, AT; Sciensano, BE; MU, CZ; VSCHT, CZ; IRFM, IT; RSU, LV; NPHSL, LT; LNS, LU; STAMI, NO; ENSP, PT; JSI, SI; NIJZ, SI; IDAEA-CSIC, ES; ISCHII, ES; KI, SE; BPI, EL; GCSL, EL) using an online collaborative platform (SharePoint; from 28.10.2022 to 11.11.2022) and finally in an online meeting (12.12.2022).

In its final version ([annex 1](#)), this online survey that aimed to collect information at the institutional level contained: a section on the general background of the respondent (country, involvement in PARC, field of work); a section on training needs (each institution could identify up to 5 topics) with topic identification, importance, target audience, difficulty level, adequacy of delivery format and, knowledge of any available training on the topic; a third section on trainers' identification (to identify which institutions had already provided training on PARC-scientific related topics, and institutions willing to provide training, and on which topics); and a final section for comments/remarks. The survey included some open-ended questions to capture as much information as the respondents would like to provide.

The survey was distributed by the National Hub Coordinators (sent by 21.12.2022) to the NHCP who forwarded it to all national hub members (PARC and non-PARC members); 06.02.2023 was established as deadline for response. A first reminder was sent on 23.01.2023 and a deadline extension (to 14.02.2023) was granted on 31.01.2023.

After duplicate and incomplete responses removal, a total of 81 valid surveys were considered for further analysis (presented below). It should be noticed that we cannot provide accurate information on response rate, as we lack

information on the number of institutions that received the survey for completion. Nevertheless, considering the total number of institutions affiliated to national hubs (n=363, considering 25 out of the 28 countries involved in PARC), we know that the obtained sample corresponds from 22,3% of the total.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Respondents

The survey was completed by 81 institutions from 25 different countries, mostly PARC members (82,7%); the distribution of responses per country is presented in Table 1 (no responses were registered from institutions from Italy, Croatia, and Israel).

Table 1. Distribution of responses by country			
		PARC member	
Country	Total (n=81)	Yes (n=67)	No (n=14)
Austria	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 10	0
Belgium	8 (9,9%)	7 (10,4%) out of 13	1 (7,1%)
Cyprus	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 2	0
Czech Republic	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 6	0
Denmark	3 (3,7%)	3 (4,5%) out of 6	0
Estonia	5 (6,2%)	3 (4,5%) out of 3	2 (14,3%)
Finland	2 (2,5%)	2 (3,0%) out of 6	0
France	9 (11,1%)	3 (4,5%) out of 17	6 (42,9%)
Germany	10 (12,3%)	8 (11,9%) out of 18	2 (14,3%)
Greece	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 7	0
Hungary	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 1	0
Iceland	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 1	0
Latvia	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 2	0
Lithuania	2 (2,5%)	2 (3,0%) out of 2	0
Luxembourg	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 4	0
Norway	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 8	0
Poland	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 4	0
Portugal	7 (8,6%)	7 (10,4%) out of 9	0

Slovakia	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 2	0
Slovenia	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,5%) out of 11	0
Spain	7 (8,6%)	7 (10,4%) out of 14	0
Sweden	7 (8,6%)	4 (6,0%) out of 13	3 (21,4%)
Switzerland	3 (3,7%)	3 (4,5%) out of 10	0
The Netherlands	4 (4,9%)	4 (6,0%) out of 9	0
United Kingdom	2 (2,5%)	2 (3%) out of 14	0

Table 2. Characterisation of respondents by institution type and field of work

Institution type	Total (n=81)	PARC member	
		Yes (n=67)	No (n=14)
Academia	32 (39,5%)	29 (43,3%)	3 (21,4%)
Research and Development	6 (7,4%)	6 (9,0%)	0
Authority/Government agency	24 (29,6%)	22 (32,8%)	2 (14,3%)
Private sector	4 (4,9%)	0	4 (28,6%)
Non-Profit organization	7 (8,7%)	3 (4,5%)	4 (28,6%)
Other	8 (9,9%)	7 (10,4%)	1 (7,1%)
Field of work*			
Epidemiology	18 (22,2%)	17 (25,4%)	1 (7,1%)
Toxicology	39 (48,1%)	33 (49,3%)	6 (42,9%)
Risk/Health impact assessment	39 (48,1%)	33 (49,3%)	6 (42,9%)
Data Science	14 (17,3%)	12 (17,9%)	2 (14,3%)
Healthcare	8 (9,9%)	5 (7,5%)	3 (21,4%)
Nutrition	6 (7,4%)	5 (7,5%)	1 (7,1%)
Microbiology	5 (6,2%)	5 (7,5%)	0
Chemical Sciences	17 (21,0%)	13 (19,4%)	4 (28,6%)
Environmental Health	45 (55,6%)	41 (61,2%)	4 (28,6%)

Public Health	21 (25,9%)	17 (25,4%)	4 (28,6%)
Social Sciences	0	0	0
Other	11 (13,6%)	7 (10,4%)	4 (28,6%)
<i>*institutions could indicate up to 3 main fields of work; percentage was calculated considering the number of valid responses in each group (total, members and non-members of PARC)</i>			

These institutions, mainly from Academia (39,5%) and Authority/Government Agencies (29,6%), reported Environmental Health (55,5%), followed by Toxicology and Risk/Health Impact Assessment (48,1%) to be their main fields of work (Table 2).

In what concerns institution involvement in PARC, respondents were mainly enrolled in WP4 – *Monitoring and exposure* (45 out of 67) and/or WP6 – *Innovation in regulatory risk assessment* (40 out of 67), followed by WP5 – *Hazard Assessment* (27 out of 67), WP2 – *A common science-policy agenda* (22 out of 67), WP9 – *Building infrastructural and human capacities* (21 out of 67), WP1 – *Coordination and Management* (19 out of 67), WP3 – *Synergies, collaborations and awareness* (18 out of 67), WP8 – *Concepts and toolboxes* (9 out of 67) and WP7 – *FAIR data* (8 out of 67).

2.2.2 Topics

In average, each respondent has indicated 2,4 topics. For reporting purposes, the 192 topics indicated by the respondents have been grouped into 43 categories (topic groups); to note that in some cases, due to their broad description, one topic response has been considered in more than one category.

For each of these categories, and as detailed in Table 3 and TableA2.1 of annex 2, we compiled information on the content suggested; the relative and absolute frequency of the topic, the importance appointed to the topic by respondents (highlighting the median value), as well as some additional data, such as preference on target audience, difficulty level, and delivery format. Available training on each of these categories, as indicated by the respondents (not yet confirmed), is also presented.

Considering the large number of topics and categories, this report presents detailed information only for the six topic groups most frequently indicated (at least eight times) in Table 3. A summary of results for the remaining 37 identified categories is presented in [annex 2](#), also in a tabular format.

As evidenced in Tables 3 and A2.1, a large amount of data has been collected with the first PARC training needs survey. The input provided by 81 institutions that work in different fields of chemical risk assessment regarding training needs, preferred contents, formats, and target audiences for training, serves as foundation for further discussions with PARC WPs (4 to 8) and task leaders in the upcoming months. The outcome of these discussions will result in PARC's training plan for Y2 and Y3.

Table 3. Summary of survey results - six main topics

Topic Category	Frequency of the topic			Importance (Mdn value)	Target audience				Difficulty level			Delivery Format					
	Total	PARC	Non-PARC		R	S	Reg	I	B	I	A	P	H	R	O		
1 Risk Assessment - Fundamentals and Approaches	29 (15,1%)	23 (79,3%)	6 (20,7%)	4	76%	21%	55%	21%	21%	69%	10%	24%NA; 24%N; 52%A	17%NA; 45%N; 38%A	21%NA; 34%N; 45%A	28%NA; 38%N; 34%A		
	<p>Description: Fundamentals of classic risk assessment; risk assessment objectives and contributions; risk assessment methodologies (deterministic and probabilistic approaches; landscape and ecological modelling); novel tools and approaches to improve risk assessment (use of new research tools or models to build the next-generation risk assessment (NGRA) regulation); holistic perspective; challenges and key-points of a next-generation risk assessment; identification of emerging chemical risks; grouping of chemicals; regulatory risk assessment. Both hands-on (real-life examples, exercises) and theoretical training (general theory, search strategy).</p> <p>Importance: Need to entail environmental reality and move towards a more holistic approach; accompany risk assessment progress towards probabilistic approaches (to apply in WP6 –Innovation in regulatory risk assessment); clarify risk assessment basics and increase knowledge on the importance and added value of risk assessment; need for coherence and understanding of risk assessment and regulation within PARC; need to derive relevant results from health impact studies; important to provide detailed knowledge on NGRA to accelerate the transition to innovation without the use of animals in research, regulatory testing and education; increase confidence in the underlying analysis (interpretation of toxicological data; insight in models to estimate exposure and risk; integration of data from NAMs) and explain the implications for decision-making.</p> <p>Available Training: (1) EFSA; (2) Karolinska Institutet online material; (3) Stockholm University: introduction to assessment and management of chemicals; (4) online materials from Wageningen University; (5) L'Association Toxicologie-Chimie (ATC), France; (6) https://www.thepsci.eu/training-videos-webinars/</p>																
	<p>Available Training: (1) EFSA; (2) Karolinska Institutet online material; (3) Stockholm University: introduction to assessment and management of chemicals; (4) online materials from Wageningen University; (5) L'Association Toxicologie-Chimie (ATC), France; (6) https://www.thepsci.eu/training-videos-webinars/</p>																
2 FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Data	11 (5,7%)	11 (100%)	0	4	100%	18%	9%	0%	55%	45%	0%	28%NA; 36%N; 36%A	27%NA; 9%N; 64%A	18%NA; 27%N; 55%A	28%NA; 36%N; 36%A		
	<p>Description: Concepts, principles, terminology, tools (publication and collaboration) and practices; implementation (harmonized, usable and operable databases); data management, banking and exploitation. Both theoretical and hands-on.</p> <p>Importance: Create PARC or other joint actions data repositories; ensure that data collected from now on is FAIR; avoid scattered data; improve understanding of FAIR among PARC members; guarantee that data and software produced by PARC has the desired impact and can be (re)used by authorities and researchers.</p> <p>Available Training: (1) NI4OS-Europe Training Platform (https://training.ni4os.eu/course/view.php?id=67); (2) GO FAIR foundation</p>																
	<p>Available Training: (1) NI4OS-Europe Training Platform (https://training.ni4os.eu/course/view.php?id=67); (2) GO FAIR foundation</p>																
3 Databases (construction, structures, management; reuse/exchange)	10 (5,2%)	8 (80,0%)	2 (20,0%)	4	82%	9%	18%	0%	20%	80%	0%	10%NA; 50%N; 40%A	10%NA; 40%N; 50%A	20%NA; 40%N; 40%A	40%NA; 40%N; 20%A		
	<p>Description: Data concepts, structures, construction/design and hosting; common vocabulary; data science; Python and SQL (Structured Query Language); relational databases. Theoretical (background, general principles) and hands-on training (practical examples, exercises).</p> <p>Importance: Better use of existing data; data harmonization; train researchers for effective and reliable data management approaches.</p> <p>Available Training: (1) Online platforms (UDEMY, Datacamp); (2) BRGM Formation (https://www.brgm.fr/en/news/news/brgm-formation-presents-its-range-training-courses-2023-develops-its-e-learning-offer)</p>																
	<p>Available Training: (1) Online platforms (UDEMY, Datacamp); (2) BRGM Formation (https://www.brgm.fr/en/news/news/brgm-formation-presents-its-range-training-courses-2023-develops-its-e-learning-offer)</p>																
4 New approach methodologies (NAMs)	9 (4,7%)	8 (88,9%)	1 (11,1%)	4	30%	20%	60%	40%	22%	67%	11%	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	23%NA; 33%N; 44%A	22%NA; 22%N; 56%A	33%NA; 56%N; 11%A		
	<p>Description: NAMs in risk assessment; principles, tools, procedures and/or databases or data sources; development; data evaluation. Theoretical; hands-on exercises; case studies and examples.</p> <p>Importance: Train experts on NAMs (increasingly used in risk assessment); reduce animal testing; increase know how to interpret and use NAMs.</p> <p>Available Training: (1) To some extent, the master's program in toxicology at Karolinska Institutet; (2) Postgraduate Education in Toxicology (PET) courses (https://toxcourses.nl/)</p>																
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Target audience: R – Researchers; S – Students; Reg – Regulators; I – Industry | **Difficulty level:** B – Beginner; I – Intermediate; A – Advanced | **Delivery Format:** P – In-person; H – Hybrid; R – Remote; O – Online resources

NA: Not adequate; N: Neutral; A: Adequate

Table 3. Summary of survey results - six main topics (cont.)

Topic Category	Frequency of the topic			Importance (Mdn value)	Target audience				Difficulty level			Delivery Format								
	Total	PARC	Non-PARC		R	S	Reg	I	B	I	A	P	H		R	O				
	8 (4,2%)	7 (87,5%)	1 (12,5%)	4	89%	56%	67%	44%	38%	38%	25%	25%NA; 12%N; 63%A		0%NA; 25%N; 75%A		0%NA; 37%N;63%A		0%NA; 37%N;63%A		
	<p>Description: Conceptual framework; development of quantitative AOPs; AOP-Wiki; weighting evidence; networks; transition from animal models to alternative models (from the perspective of human health); sequential chains of causally linked events of toxicological effects spanning over layers of biological organization; pertinent models to safety assessment of chemicals; rationale behind the description of an AOP based on real cases; holistic understanding of the underlying biological mechanisms and processes involved in toxicokinetic (TK); application for regulatory purposes; contribution to decision making. Theoretical and computational training on AOP development and available software, pipelines.</p>																			
5	Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs)	<p>Importance: Increase hands-on experience in developing AOPs; have a better overview of the scientific specificities of animal models and of non-animal models, their weaknesses and strengths to establish the next-generation risk safety assessment; understand AOPs because they are becoming the toxicological knowledge framework that will support chemical risk assessment; understand information needed for building a mechanistic AOP and how to apply them for risk assessment; identify pipelines to be followed and for partners to understand and raise relevant concerns/suggestions early in the project; understand and identify available mechanistic information to describe causality; provide a more accurate and efficient way of predicting toxicity and risk assessment; provide a transparent and scientifically defensible approach to the evaluation of potential hazard and risk, enabling better decision making in regulatory processes and product development.</p> <p>Available Training: (1) To some extent, the master's program in toxicology at Karolinska Institutet; (2) L'Association Toxicologie-Chimie (ATC), France, (3) International Training in Health Risk Assessment, Karolinska Institutet; (4) Postgraduate Education in Toxicology (PET) courses (https://toxcourses.nl/)</p>																		
	8 (4,2%)	7 (87,5%)	1 (12,5%)	4	100%	13%	13%	0%	13%	75%	13%	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A		12%NA; 63%N; 25%A		12%NA; 50%N;38%A		38%NA; 38%N;24%A		
6	Statistical analysis	<p>Importance: Need to provide evidence based scientific conclusions; need to handle and make sense of large and complex datasets; need to keep up with state-of-the-art methods; need to properly train toxicologists in statistical methods; need to harmonize data analysis; need to learn new statistical methods to deal with exposure mixtures, multiple endpoints, ecotoxicological data (single species, multiple species, mixture toxicity, toxicokinetics).</p> <p>Available Training: (1) www.biostat.epi.org/; (2) 1-week course organized by University of Aveiro (https://www.ua.pt/pt/dbio/cursos-avancados)</p>																		

Target audience: R – Researchers; S – Students; Reg – Regulators; I – Industry | **Difficulty level:** B – Beginner; I – Intermediate; A – Advanced | **Delivery Format:** P – In-person; H – Hybrid; R – Remote; O – Online resources

NA: Not adequate; N: Neutral; A: Adequate

Considering that PARC has budgeted for about six in-person training events over the next 2 years, it becomes evident that many of these topic groups need to be combined to constitute the content of each of those events. An initial exercise of grouping topics into larger subjects is presented in Figure 1. Further details on topic grouping and prioritization are provided in section 3.2.

Figure 1. Training topics categories grouped under main areas.

2.2.3 Trainers' identification

Nearly half (44,4%; n=36) of the responding institutions indicated to have previously provided training in PARC related scientific topics (32 out of these 36 are PARC members). Gathering information about past training events has a dual benefit. Firstly, it confirms that PARC partners have expertise in conducting training activities related to some of the identified training topics. Secondly, materials relevant to these topics may have already been prepared and are available, which can expedite the organization of upcoming training events.

The number of institutions available to carry out training under PARC was marginally higher (49,4%, n=40; 32 of them are PARC members). Figure 2 shows the number of institutions with experience in providing training in the 8 main areas above identified, alongside the number of those available to participate as trainers in the future. The identification of institutions with previous expertise in training, and available for future training in the different topics will be of great value for the upcoming task of training plan definition.

Figure 2. Responding institutions that had provided training in the 8 main areas of work; and their willingness to provide training in the future in these same areas.

2.3 Lessons learned

Two major issues must be addressed in the future: 1) questionnaire formulation; and 2) survey distribution and dissemination.

The analysis of data obtained in the first PARC training needs survey showed that many of the respondents provided similar input in topic description and topic importance. For instance, some respondents indicated "Non-target screening" as the topic description and mentioned a "basic course on NTS and data treatment workflow in particular" as the comment on the topic importance. Therefore, in the next training needs survey, some of the questions will be altered to avoid overlapping responses. Ultimately, it will be necessary to better clarify what is intended in each question.

Understanding and increasing the representativeness of data collected is also a concern for the future, and for that purpose we will (1) ask national hubs to provide information on the number of institutions to which the survey was distributed; (2) include an option in the survey to indicate that there are no training needs to report; and (3) improve the visibility of the training needs survey by announcing the survey response period in PARC website, newsletter, and social media.

2.4 Training held in PARC Y1

Considering the rationale behind Task 9.4, that consists of setting a training plan fitted to PARC partners and stakeholders (as detailed in section 3.2) based on their reported needs, there were no training events carried out under Task 9.4 in Y1. Nonetheless, considering some WP's needs for immediate activities' implementation, WP6 and WP7 have organized some internal training, on their own responsibility and criteria, as detailed below; WP4, WP5, and WP8 did not conduct any training events along Y1.

2.4.1 WP6 – Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

Training on **Data upload to MCRA (Monte Carlo Risk Assessment) toolbox** has been organized by RIVM (National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, The Netherlands) for Task 6.2 partners. This was a 2.5-hour synchronous remote course (with all participants online in simultaneous) held at three different timeslots in November 2022. This short hands-on course was focused on the upload of human biomonitoring data and relative potency factors (RPFs) in the MCRA toolbox, and on the use of RPFs for risk assessment (making use of the PFAS risk assessment performed by European Food Safety Authority as an example). Further details on dates, trainers and lectures are available in [annex 3](#).

Also under Task 6.2, short 2-hour training on **Using MCRA with PBK models** and on **Using MCRA for analyzing exposure mixtures in Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data** were carried out in a hybrid format (in-person in Athens with remote participants) in November 2022, by the Biometrics Group of the Wageningen University & Research (The Netherlands). **Using MCRA with PBK models** was dedicated to the use of dietary exposure models and PBK models to calculate probabilistic internal exposure distributions, coupling of PBK models to MCRA and other uses, such as aggregate exposure, and in vitro -in vivo extrapolation. **Using MCRA for analyzing exposure mixtures in HBM data** focused on the statistical models in MCRA to analyze HBM data for main exposures and mixtures, and cluster analysis for identification of subgroups with similar exposure patterns. Additional information on dates, trainers, and lectures is available in [annex 3](#).

2.4.2 WP7 – FAIR Data

The GO FAIR Foundation (GFF) will provide support to PARC, and specifically WP7 in the first two years of the project, with the FAIR assessment of the chemical risk assessment data landscape, development of roadmaps for FAIR practices implementation, development of specific data models, ontologies, and shared vocabularies. In addition, GFF will also provide a Train-the-Trainer program, to train and certify a group of 10 to 20 researchers from PARC members that will become independent facilitators of PARC FAIRification activities. These training activities will be fully coordinated by GFF and WP7.

In Y1, an in-person FAIR awareness training of 2 hours was held in Brno, Czech Republic, in October 2022. A FAIR Data & Tools Webinar Series, detailed in [annex 3](#) is ongoing; videos will be made available on the PARC website.

2.5 Materials' development to support future training

A registration form and training activities evaluation survey to be used by local training organizers have already been developed and refined by Task 9.4 partners. To obtain further information on training needs on PARC topics, the training evaluation survey also includes a few questions on training needs; these responses will be considered when establishing the new training plan for Y4-Y6. A certificate template has also been prepared and adapted to PARC layout by WP3.2.

These materials are available to all PARC partners (ANSES Sharepoint), not only to provide support to local organizers but also to ensure a harmonized visual graphical language amongst project partners, and harmonization in data collection regarding training satisfaction for future analysis.

3. Future activities

3.1 Mapping existing training

Taking into consideration the results of this first training needs survey, partners will now search for existing training courses and programs, and pinpoint existing learning resources that meet the identified training needs, starting by confirming those indicated by respondents. Existing training courses and materials will be disseminated through PARC website.

3.2 Training plan

Building on data collected in the first PARC training needs survey, on the existing training map, and on WP and task leaders' input (on contents; timing; possible trainers/scientific coordinators; necessary facilities; adequate duration; and topics' grouping), Task 9.4 co-leaders will work on topic prioritization. This will include general aspects (Is there existing training that can fill in this gap?); Why (Why should this training be done?; Is the deficiency tied to a need? Is the gap tied to a task (internal)?); Who (Trainers – do we have them? Do we have the necessary facilities? Who is the trainee for this training? And how many? What is known about them to help design and customize this training? What other groups might benefit from training?), How (Which is the best format? How can this gap be broken down into teachable parts?), and When (When will the training be presented? Best timing considering WP tasks timing, work cycles, and holidays) analysis.

A training plan proposal will be discussed with WP and task leaders, and an outline of training courses and learning resources to be held/developed within PARC in Y2 and Y3 will be prepared (training plan to be delivered by M18; AD9.1).

To comply with the available training budget, the training plan will include different training formats, namely online courses and online resources (respondents have already provided some valuable information on which topics could be considered in such formats). In parallel, to facilitate staff exchange (one-to-one training), and promote an efficient and effective transfer of skills and knowledge among project partners, Task 9.4 co-leaders will circulate a form in the next few months, to identify research groups available to host researchers. A period of applications broadcasted on the website will follow.

4. Final remarks

In this first year with the online training needs survey, a considerable amount of valuable information has been collected regarding the gaps and needs in expertise on PARC scientific-related topics that will feed upcoming activities. Our main challenge is to map existing training, prioritize and group topics to cover as many of them as possible in the next two years. Additional challenges include the limited budget available for training that may limit partners' and stakeholders' participation (some of these concerns have already been identified by partners in the survey). The organization of remote events and development of open online resources may be a possible way to overcome these restrictions.

As for the initially identified risk of lack of capacity within PARC to provide training in certain topics, this seems to be true for certain areas, such as Risk Communication, and Chemicals Regulation and Policy. Considering that many PARC members have not answered to the survey, we believe that we may still have internal experts for this topic, in case these topics get prioritized; if not, we will explore possible cooperation with existing (international) training programs.

Annex 1 – PARC Training Needs Survey

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC)

European partnership

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014

Co-funded by
the European Union

PARC TRAINING NEEDS SURVEY

Survey Context

Task 9.4 'Training' of WP9 'Building infrastructural and human capacities' of the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) project is responsible for i) mapping training needs, ii) collecting and compiling training opportunities, and iii) providing support for the organization of training.

To capture training needs in PARC-scientific related topics, Task 9.4 is now distributing among PARC partners, and stakeholders (through national hubs contact points) the first **PARC's Training Needs Survey**. Information collected at the **institutional level** will help Task 9.4 team to comply and strategically prioritize training(s) to be carried out up to M42 of PARC (October 2025), with the identified training needs and the objectives of the PARC project.

Therefore, please put aside sufficient time to collect information on the training needs of those working in your institution and complete this survey as accurately as possible to ensure that you have covered the current as well as emerging needs for training and capacity building in the era of next-generation risk assessment.

PARC objectives

PARC is an EU-wide research and innovation partnership program to support EU and national chemical risk assessment and risk management bodies with new data, knowledge, methods, networks, and skills to address current, emerging, and novel chemical safety challenges.

PARC organizes its activities to reach three specific objectives:

1. An EU-wide sustainable cross-disciplinary network to identify and agree on research and innovation needs and to support research uptake into regulatory chemical risk assessment.
2. Joint EU research and innovation activities responding to identified priorities in support of current regulatory risk assessment processes for chemical substances and to emerging challenges.
3. Strengthening existing capacities and building new transdisciplinary platforms to support chemical risk assessment of next generation.

Data management

Data obtained from this survey will be saved and stored by the National Institute of Health Dr. Ricardo Jorge, Portugal (INSA); names and email contacts will be removed from the database before transfer to Task 9.4 key partners that will also participate in data analysis. Data management and handling will follow the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU (2016/679). Results of the survey will become available by May 2023.

Deadline for completion: You may save your entries and continue later, but be sure to submit it before **06.02.2023**

If you have any questions, please contact Carla Trindade Costa (carla.trindade@insa.min-saude.pt).

Thank you for taking the time and focus to complete this survey.

Task 9.4 leaders

João Paulo Teixeira & Carla Trindade Costa

NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF HEALTH DOUTOR RICARDO JORGE

Porto | Portugal

www.insa.min-saude.pt

(all questions are mandatory except if clearly indicated)

Consent

Do you confirm that you have read this information and that you agree that information provided may be used for project purposes, such as project reports, scientific articles, presentations and exchange among partners in the terms mentioned above?	Yes/No (one option)
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Institutional contact point/ person of contact (for the purpose of this survey)

Name	Open field <120 ca
Email address	Email address field

I. Institution characterisation

1. Institution name	Open field >120 ca
2. Country	Open field <120 ca
3. Institution type	<p>Multiple choice (one option)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia • R&D • Authority/government agency • Private sector • Non-profit organisation • Other <p>IF Other 3.1 Please specify "Other" (open field <120 ca)</p>
4. Institution field(s) of work (up to three options)	<p>Multiple choice (up to three options)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epidemiology • Toxicology • Risk/Health Impact assessment • Data Science (e.g., modelling) • Healthcare (e.g., medicine, nursing) • Nutrition • Microbiology • Chemical Sciences • Environmental Health • Public Health • Social Sciences

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other 1 • Other 2 • Other 3 <p>IF Other 1 4.1 Please specify first "Other" (open field <120 ca)</p> <p>IF Other 2 4.2 Please specify second "Other" (open field <120 ca)</p> <p>IF Other 3 4.3 Please specify third "Other" (open field <120 ca)</p>
<p>5. Are you a partner in PARC?</p>	<p>Yes/No (one option)</p> <p>IF YES 5.1. In which of the WPs of PARC are you involved?</p> <p>Multiple Choice (more than one option is possible)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1: Coordination and management • WP2: A common science-policy agenda • WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness • WP4: Monitoring and exposure • WP5: Hazard assessment • WP6: Innovation in regulatory risk assessment • WP7: FAIR data • WP8: Concepts and toolboxes • WP9: Building infrastructural and human capacities

II. Training topics

Considering PARC objectives, please list up to 5 training topics you would like to see addressed in PARC training plan.

TOPIC 1

<p>1. Topic description Please provide here some details to describe your view on this particular need; e.g., contents, hands-on vs. theoretical, etc.</p>	<p>Open field >120 ca</p>
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<p>2. Importance of the topic In your opinion, how important is it to address this topic?</p>	<p>Ranking 1-5 1. slightly important; 2. important; 3. fairly important; 4. very important; 5. extremely important</p>
<p>2.1 Please comment:</p>	<p>Open field >120 ca</p>
<p>3. Target audience In your opinion, who will benefit the most of this training? Please justify.</p>	<p>Open field >120 ca</p>
<p>4. Difficulty level In your opinion, which would be the most adequate level of difficulty for this training?</p>	<p>Multiple choice (one option)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beginner • Intermediate • Advanced
<p>5. Delivery format For this topic, please indicate which delivery format do you find to be the most adequate, by rating the different options here presented.</p>	<p>Likert 3 (not adequate; neutral; adequate)</p> <p>In-person (trainees and instructors gather in the same physical location, at the same time)</p> <p>Hybrid (online activities are mixed with in-person meetings)</p> <p>Remote (all the learning takes place online; it may be a mixture of asynchronous and synchronous activities, or exclusively synchronous)</p> <p>Online resources (all the learning takes place online, with all required activities happening asynchronously)</p>
<p>6. Available training Are you aware of any existing training on this topic?</p>	<p>Yes/No (one option)</p> <p>IF YES 6.1. Please provide details (Open field >120 ca)</p>
<p>Do you wish to add another topic?</p>	<p>Yes/No (one option)</p> <p>IF YES REPEAT QUESTIONS 1-6 of section II (Up to 5 Topics; only the first is mandatory)</p>

III. Trainer's identification

1. Has your institution ever provided training on PARC-scientific related topics?	Yes/No (one option) If YES 1.1. In which topics? (open field >120 ca)
2. Would your institution be willing to provide training on PARC-scientific related topics?	Yes/No (one option) If YES 2.1. In which topics? (open field >120 ca)

IV. Final Comments*Not mandatory*

Please include here any general remarks, or comments you would like to add regarding training that were not addressed above.	Open field >120 ca
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End of the survey

Thank you for taking the time and focus to complete this survey.

LINK: <https://survey-insa.min-saude.pt/redcap/surveys/?s=HHAMXKJXNW>

Annex 2 – Summary of survey results

Topic Category	Frequency of the topic			Importance (Min value)	Target audience				Difficulty level				Delivery Format			
	Total	PARC	Non-PARC		R	S	Reg	I	B	I	A	P	H	R	O	
7 New methods (and biomarkers) for new chemicals Description: New analytical methods for contaminants; biomarker identification; innovative methods and tools for human biomonitoring and quantification of chemicals in environment (soil, air, water, and food). Theoretical and hands-on training (practical examples, exercises, visits to laboratories, set-up of proficiency tests) Importance: To characterize exposure to new chemicals currently used in various consumer products; ensure the availability of adequate analytical methods for the (inter)national laboratories; obtain experience and knowledge in analytical methods available for chemicals' quantification Available Training: none reported	6 (3,1%)	5 (83,3%)	1 (16,7%)	4	100%	0%	17%	33%	0%	67%	33%	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0N; 50%A	33%NA; 17%N; 50%A	
8 Method Quality Control/Assurance Description: Quality assurance and quality control of chemical analysis (OECD, CRED & SCIRAP); interlab trials Importance: Increase laboratorial capacity; harmonize processes, selection of methods and analytical (testing) work in laboratories of different countries; increase results' reliability Available Training: none reported	6 (3,1%)	6 (100,0%)	0	3,5	100%	0%	50%	33%	17%	67%	17%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	66%NA; 17%N; 17%A	67%NA; 33%N; 0%A	
9 Exposure science Description: Exposure assessment; modelling of exposure and biomonitoring data; geospatial modelling of data; aggregate exposure models; TK/TD models for aggregating exposure routes Importance: Better assess exposure to assess risk; apply uniform methodologies; train partners in TK/TD models for aggregating oral, inhalation and dermal exposures Available Training: none reported	6 (3,1%)	5 (83,3%)	1 (16,7%)	4	83%	0%	17%	17%	0%	100%	0%	33%NA; 17%N; 50%A	0%NA; 67%N; 33%A	33%NA; 17%N; 50%A	33%NA; 17%N; 50%A	
10 Standardized sample collection, processing and Biobanking Description: Standardized sampling; sample processing, shipment of human biological materials including ethical and legal guidelines (biological safety); sample storage & biobanking. Importance: Increase knowledge on standardized sampling of human biological materials and related processes including shipment and legal aspects, e.g., demands on biological safety and hence increase the use of respective SOPs and harmonization of field work; guarantee uniformity and reproducibility. Available Training: none reported	6 (3,1%)	5 (83,3%)	1 (16,7%)	4	100%	0%	0%	17%	0%	67%	33%	17%NA; 0%N; 83%A	50%NA; 17%N; 33%A	50%NA; 33%N; 17%A	50%NA; 33%N; 17%A	
11 (Inter)national context Description: Mapping of the different regulations and implementation in Europe and national scale; chemical substance monitoring (scope of application, plans, regulations, risks, chemicals lifecycle); cases (endocrine disruptors; contaminants in the food chain) Importance: Understand regulatory requirements and needs of the data/methods researcher/producer; increase knowledge on the steps and criteria to establish regulations of chemical substances, for obtaining authorization to be commercialized, and the regulatory bodies involved and their competence; gain a basic understanding of the different procedures and responsibilities of chemical regulations in Europe Available Training: none reported	6 (3,1%)	3 (50,0%)	3 (50,0%)	4	83%	0%	17%	50%	0%	100%	0%	33%NA; 17%N; 50%A	17%NA; 17%N; 66%A	17%NA; 50%N; 33%A	50%NA; 33%N; 17%A	
12 Physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modeling Description: PBK modeling and use in risk assessment. Hands-on. Importance: Understand principles of the different models; how to use different models and platforms; identify critical parameters that affect the end results and uncertainties related to models; understand model validation and calibration approaches; integrate new approach methods. Available Training: (1) To some extent, the master's program in toxicology at Karolinska Institutet; (2) Certara (https://www.certara.com/training/); (3) Postgraduate Education in Toxicology (PET) courses (https://toxcourses.nl/); (4) Wageningen University	6 (3,1%)	6 (100,0%)	0	4	67%	50%	83%	50%	33%	50%	17%	17%NA; 33%N; 50%A	33%NA; 17%N; 50%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 17%N; 83%A	
13 Integrative approaches to testing and assessment (IATAs) Description: IAT development; its use in risk assessment (regulatory and industry point of view); approach, toolbox, weight of evidence, and reporting Importance: Improve the accuracy and efficiency of toxicity assessments; combine multiples sources of information; promote harmonization, and advance understanding of toxicity, to include it in next generation risk assessment; improve safety assessment, decision making, communication, and data quality Available Training: none reported	6 (3,1%)	6 (100,0%)	0	4	83%	50%	100%	33%	17%	67%	17%	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	17%NA; 0%N; 83%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	17%NA; 0%N; 83%A	
14 Mixture Risk Assessment Description: Principles and methods; limitations Importance: Better translate science to policy; improve skills on assessing real life exposures; further advance risk assessment science; increase the confidence in the underlying analysis Available Training: RIVM	6 (3,1%)	6 (100,0%)	0	4	67%	17%	83%	33%	0%	83%	17%	17%NA; 17%N; 66%A	17%NA; 17%N; 66%A	17%NA; 33%N; 50%A	50%NA; 33%N; 17%A	
15 Questionnaires Description: Data collection harmonization; data management; online tools (RedCap and e-Consent) use and limitations Importance: Harmonize fieldwork; move towards paperless systems Available Training: Online RedCap webpage	5 (2,6%)	4 (80,0%)	1 (20,0%)	4	100%	0%	0%	20%	40%	40%	20%	40%NA; 0%N; 60%A	60%NA; 0%N; 40%A	20%NA; 20%N; 60%A	40%NA; 20%N; 40%A	
16 Computational Toxicology Description: In silico toxicology; QSAR toolbox and other freely available in silico tools. Hands-on training Importance: Understand the basics of computational toxicology, including strengths and limitations; decrease animal testing; identify and discuss possible pipelines Available Training: To some extent in the master's programme in toxicology at Karolinska Institutet	5 (2,6%)	4 (80,0%)	1 (20,0%)	4	80%	60%	20%	20%	20%	80%	0%	0%NA; 40%N; 60%A	0%NA; 20%N; 80%A	0%NA; 40%N; 60%A	0%NA; 80%N; 20%A	
17 Risk Communication Description: Innovative risk communication patterns and tools; adaptation to fast-paced digital age; Communication to general public Importance: Train skills on risk communication (to the public; between sectors and professionals); need to know how to communicate uncertainties Available Training: (1) EFSA; (2) WHO CRA Network	5 (2,6%)	5 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	80%	20%	20%	80%	0%	20%NA; 0%N; 80%A	0%NA; 40%N; 60%A	40%NA; 0%N; 60%A	40%NA; 40%N; 20%A	

Target audience: R – Researchers; S – Students; Reg – Regulators; I – Industry | **Difficulty level:** B – Beginner; I – Intermediate; A – Advanced | **Delivery Format:** P – In-person; H – Hybrid; R – Remote; O – Online resources

NA: Not adequate; N: Neutral; A: Adequate

Table A2.1. Summary of survey results on 37 categories (out of the 43 identified) (cont)																
Topic Category	Frequency of the topic			Importance (Mdn value)	Target audience				Difficulty level			Delivery Format				
	Total	PARC	Non-PARC		R	S	Reg	I	B	I	A	P	H	R	O	
18 Non-targeted screening Description: Use of non-targeted screening to identify new emerging contaminants; case of high-resolution mass spectrometry (instrumental setup, data management and interpretation). Theoretical and practical training Importance: Increase capacity building; need to produce high quality data; harmonize non-target screening approaches Available Training: EAWAG, Switzerland	4 (2,1%)	4 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	25%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%NA; 75%N; 25%A	25%NA; 0%N; 75%A	0%NA; 75%N; 25%A	25%NA; 50%N; 25%A
19 In vitro in vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) Description: Modelling; risk assessment requirements Importance: Need for harmonized training; train researchers Available Training: Postgraduate Education in Toxicology (PET) courses (https://toxcourses.nl/)	4 (2,1%)	3 (75,0%)	1 (25,0%)	3,5	100%	50%	50%	25%	25%	50%	25%	25%NA; 25%N; 50%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	25%NA; 0%N; 75%A	
20 Ethical issues Description: no details provided Importance: no details provided Available Training: none reported	3 (1,6%)	3 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	0%	0%	33%	67%	0%	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	
21 Strategy for Sustainability Description: Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) concept and implementation; tools; chemicals' substitution. Theoretical (conceptual thinking on SSbD) and practical (tools and application) Importance: Need to operationalize the CSS chemical strategy; create awareness on CSS Available Training: Delft University, The Netherlands	3 (1,6%)	1 (33,3%)	2 (66,7%)	4	100%	0%	33%	100%	33%	67%	0%	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 67%N; 33%A	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	
22 One Health Description: Interlinkage between Environment and Health; definitions and perspectives Importance: To discuss the interlinkages between environment and health; to prioritize OneHealth; understand differences in definitions and concepts in different areas of research Available Training: none reported	3 (1,6%)	2 (66,7%)	1 (33,3%)	4	33%	0%	100%	0%	33%	67%	0%	33%NA; 0%N; 67%A	0%NA; 67%N; 33%A	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	
23 REACH Description: Chemicals impact and labelling Importance: Need to comply with REACH guidelines; raise awareness on chemicals' risks Available Training: WECF France (https://wecf-france.org/sante-environnement/decouvri-le-projet-nesting/)	3 (1,6%)	1 (33,3%)	2 (66,7%)	5	67%	0%	33%	67%	67%	33%	0%	67%NA; 0%N; 33%A	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	0%NA; 33%N; 67%A	0%NA; 67%N; 33%A	
24 In vitro testing Description: Good practices (OECD guidelines); reduction of the use of components/products of animal origin in cell culture (animal-free alternative); 3D cell culture models Importance: Improve robustness and reproducibility of in vitro methods; reduce animal components in cell culture; obtain knowledge on 3D cell culture models for toxicological assessments Available Training: https://ivivis.org/topic/givimp/	3 (1,6%)	2 (66,7%)	1 (33,3%)	3	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	67%	33%	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	67%NA; 0%N; 33%A	33%NA; 0%N; 67%A	33%NA; 33%N; 33%A	
25 Data compilation and review Description: Data search (literature, databases, etc.); text mining tools; meta-analysis. Theoretical and hands-on Importance: Increase know how to carry out a meta-analysis Available Training: none reported	3 (1,6%)	2 (66,7%)	1 (33,3%)	5	100%	0%	33%	0%	33%	33%	33%	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	33%NA; 67%N; 0%A	0%NA; 67%N; 33%A	33%NA; 67%N; 0%A	
26 Method development and optimization Description: Innovative methods development (e.g. high-throughput identification of protein targets from any chemical or mixture); method optimization (e.g. chromatographic analysis of cytostatic drugs). Theoretical and practical training Importance: no details provided Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	1 (50,0%)	1 (50,0%)	4	100%	0%	0%	50%	0%	50%	50%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	50%NA; 50%N; 0%A	
27 Methodological harmonization/SOP Description: Implementation of existing SOPs; chemical analysis alignment Importance: Harmonize methods (chemical analysis) and procedures Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	2	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	
28 Established HBM Programs (sustainability) Description: Lessons from countries with established programs; legislative anchoring; sources of funding; ecosystem requirements; HBM for policy decisions; setting up sustainable activities at national level (e.g. human biomonitoring, data storage and access) Importance: Support partners to develop sustainable networks at a national level Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	50%	0%	0%	50%	50%	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	50%NA; 50%N; 0%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	
29 HBM for Risk Assessment Description: Concepts; HBM in toxicology; HBM in regulatory RA; new tools Importance: Produce useful HBM data for risk assessment Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	50%	100%	100%	0%	100%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	
30 Recruitment strategies Description: no details provided Importance: Train experts on practical aspects of running HBM surveys Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	5	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	50%	50%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	

Target audience: R – Researchers; S – Students; Reg – Regulators; I – Industry | Difficulty level: B – Beginner; I – Intermediate; A – Advanced | Delivery Format: P – In-person; H – Hybrid; R – Remote; O – Online resources

NA: Not adequate; N: Neutral; A: Adequate

Table A2.1. Summary of survey results on 37 categories (out of the 43 identified) (cont)																	
Topic Category	Frequency of the topic			Importance (Mdn value)	Target audience				Difficulty level			Delivery Format					
	Total	PARC	Non-PARC		R	S	Reg	I	B	I	A	P	H	R	O		
31 Decision making process Description: Policy translation of scientific results on regional and national level; decision making in regulatory settings (data used, integration of new approaches) Importance: Improve interaction between regulators and scientists; understand data/information required for decision making Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	50%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	50%NA; 50%N; 0%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	
32 Basic Toxicology Description: no details provided Importance: Improve knowledge of policy makers and competent authorities Available Training: none provided	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	3	100%	0%	50%	50%	100%	0%	0%	0%	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	
33 Burden of Disease Description: Calculation of Disability-Adjusted Life Years attributable to chemical exposures. Theoretical and hands-on training Importance: Demonstrate impact of chemicals Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	4,5	50%	100%	100%	50%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	50%NA; 50%N; 0%A	
34 Uncertainty Description: Assessment and reporting; genetic and preconditioned backgrounds. Theoretical Importance: Improve the quality and reliability of risk assessments; increase transparency and confidence in risk management decisions Available Training: none reported	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	4,5	100%	50%	100%	100%	0%	50%	50%	0%	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	
35 Cases studies (pesticides, natural toxins, climate change) Description: Pesticides; natural toxins; climate change Importance: no details provided Available Training: EFSA	2 (1,0%)	2 (100,0%)	0	3	0%	50%	0%	50%	50%	50%	0%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 50%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	50%NA; 0%N; 50%A	
36 Method validation and performance Description: Method validation (OECD guidelines); method performance Importance: Characterize method performance; define minimum performance levels; improve results' reproducibility Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	
37 HBM in crisis situations Description: no details provided Importance: Expand work initiated in HBM4EU Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	
38 New (non-invasive) matrices Description: Sampling; e.g. exhaled breath condensate Importance: Expand knowledge on new samples and sampling techniques Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	2	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	
39 Data mining Description: Identification of high quality data sets; minimal quality standards Importance: no details provided Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	100%	100%	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	
40 Animal models Description: Animal models in ecotoxicology Importance: Provide practical knowledge on different animal models useful for ecotoxicological testing (suitability, maintaining, testing procedures, etc.) (e.g. Daphnia magna, Caenorhabditis elegans, Drosophila melanogaster...) Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	
41 Effect biomarkers Description: Genetic/epigenetic biomarkers; context and importance within chemical risk assessment and exposure studies. Theoretical and hands-on Importance: Improve knowledge on the importance of genetics and epigenetics in exposure assessment Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	100%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	
42 BMD modeling Description: Principles and practices. Theoretical and hands-on Importance: Apply BMD modelling in risk assessment Available Training: none reported	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	
43 Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) Description: Web-based platform; models available; use in regulatory risk assessment. Hands-on training Importance: Improve data quality; improve transparency; increase confidence in risk assessment; improve decision making Available Training: (1) Wageningen University, Bioinformatics; (2) RIVM	1 (0,5%)	1 (100,0%)	0	4	100%	0%	100%	100%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	0%NA; 0%N; 100%A	0%NA; 100%N; 0%A	100%NA; 0%N; 0%A	

Target audience: R – Researchers; S – Students; Reg – Regulators; I – Industry | Difficulty level: B – Beginner; I – Intermediate; A – Advanced | Delivery Format: P – In-person; H – Hybrid; R – Remote; O – Online resources

NA: Not adequate; N: Neutral; A: Adequate

Annex 3 – Training held PARC Y1

Training upload HBM data to MCRA

There is one training, which will be offered on three timeslots. Please chose one of the timeslots using the registration form.

Date 1: Monday 7 November 9.30-12.00

Date 2: Monday 11 November 9.30-12.00

Date 3: Monday 11 November 13.30-16.00

Venue: virtual training using MS TEAMS. Gerda van Donkersgoed will send all registered persons instructions and an MS Teams invitation.

Fake HBM data. We will start working with a fake HBM data set to avoid GDPR issues. The learning goal is to get hands-on with MCRA and to understand the upload your own files procedure. We will discuss how to organize data sharing or data curation, and which requirements are being set, during the fourth PARC real-life mixture consortium meeting.

Tutors: Jacob van Klaveren (RIVM), Gerda van Donkersgoed (RIVM) and Johannes Kruijselbrink (Wageningen Research).

Monday morning 7th and Friday morning 11th.

9:30 – 9:45	Welcome and round table
9:45 – 10:00	Lecture L1 and E1: how to get connected to MCRA - what is a workspace and how actions can be performed
10:00 – 10:30	Hands-on training E2: Description and use of the MCRA software uploading your data. You will be trained how to upload hazard RPF data (real data set) and how to upload HBM data (fake data set).
10:30 – 10:45	Hands-on training E3: How to use your own data e.g. new relative potency factors.
10:45 – 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 – 11:45	Exercise E4: how your HBM data can be used in an MCRA workspace (fake data set). At this stage it is a try-out to understand MCRA. During the Athens meeting more guidance on MCRA and data storage will be given.
11.45 – 12:00	General Discussion

Friday afternoon 11th.

13:00 – 13:45	Welcome and round table
13:45 – 14:00	Lecture L1 and E1: how to get connected to MCRA - what is a workspace and how actions can be performed
14:00 – 14:30	Hands-on training E2: Description and use of the MCRA software uploading your data. You will be trained how to upload hazard RPF data (real data set) and how to upload HBM data (fake data set).
14:30 – 14:45	Hands-on training E3: How to use your own data e.g. new relative potency factors.
14:45 – 15:00	Coffee Break
15:00 – 15:45	Exercise E4: how your HBM data can be used in an MCRA workspace (fake data set). At this stage it is a try-out to understand MCRA. During the Athens meeting more guidance on MCRA and data storage will be given.
15.45 – 16:00	General Discussion

PARC FAIR Data & Tools Webinar Series

- a. 26/01/2023: FAIR Awareness (Erik Schultes - GO FAIR Foundation)
- b. 09/02/2023: Experience as a Data Shepherd in NanoCommons (Dr. Anastasios Papadiamantis - UoB)
- c. 23/02/2023: FAIR Implementation Profiles – Introduction & their use PARC (Barbara Magagna - GO FAIR Foundation)
- d. 09/03/2023: Visualisation of complex experimental workflows (Dr. Thomas Exner - SevenPastNine)
- e. 23/03/2023: Making (nano)toxicity data FAIR – experiences from Gov4Nano & Data Re-use examples (Dr. Penny Nymark - Karolinska University)